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Multi-Agent Systems in support of Digital Twins: a Survey

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Abstract. The joint use of technologies such as Internet of Things, Artificial Intelligence, Cloud Computing or Virtualization has fostered the development of digital twins (DT). A DT is described as a physical entity, its virtual counterpart and the data connections between both. Digital twins are increasingly being used to enrich physical entities by exploiting different computational approaches, which are applied to the virtual twin part. One of such approaches is the multi-agent systems (MAS) paradigm. It is claimed they resemble DT in many features. In order to analysis the suitability of MAS for DT, this paper presents the results of a systematic literature review focused on the analysis of current proposals exploiting multi-agent systems to support the design of digital twins. We found that the integrating the multi-agent paradigm with digital twins can be challenging, because the distinction among them is sometimes blurry. Moreover, it has been detected that MAS are generally the interaction environment for the DTs, and data of the DTs allow agents' better decisions to be made in real time. That is, the massive volume of data stored by the DT allows agents to make decisions based on these data, and on the other hand, MAS shapes the environment where the DTs operate and interact.

Keywords: Digital Twin, Multi-Agent systems.

1. Introduction

In recent decades, the development of technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence, Cloud Computing or Virtualization have contributed to the digitization of different assets, systems and processes [25]. The integration of these technologies has given origin to digital twins (DT), which are likely to be one of the most important developments in the field of technology in the next years. A digital twin is often described as a physical entity, a virtual counterpart, and the data connections between the two. They are gaining more and more interest due to their significant potential in many applications fields [2].

One of the approaches that has many similarities to DT is Multi-Agent Systems (MAS) [25]. MAS are agent-based systems that act as an external entity operating in a specific environment while scanning and collecting data [7]. Although some authors have already sketched the idea of exploiting MAS for developing DT [25][14], no previous work has been proposed up to now that focuses on investigating the relationship between these two concepts: "Digital Twin" and "Multi-agent". This paper analyzes whether this relationship exists or not and how they may complement each other.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes digital twin technology and multi-agent systems. Then, Section 3 describes the methodology used for the study. Next, section 4 shows the analysis carried out to answer the stated research question. And finally, section 5 presents both the conclusions drawn and our future work.

2. Related works

The Digital Twin (DT) concept was originally coined by Grieves and Vicker in 2003 [11]. The DT model proposal, as depicted in Fig. 1, was made up by three elements: i) a real space with physical objects, ii) a virtual space with virtual objects, and iii) a link between the two spaces for the bi-directional flow of data between real and virtual spaces allowing the convergence of physical and virtual systems.

Fig. 1. Grieves' digital twin model (adapted from [11]).

Up to now, a widely accepted definition of DT has not been achieved, neither a process for developing and deploying DT. Several attempts can be found in the literature that pursue this purpose. For example, [2, 14, 25] gather different definitions extracted from other proposals as well as the main characteristics that a DT should feature. These authors do converge, at a high level, in defining a Digital Twin as a computer model that simulates the life of a physical entity, such as an object, a process, a person, or some of these characteristics. However, as claimed in [2], a DT is more than a simple simulation, a DT is a living, intelligent and evolving model. It follows the lifecycle of its physical twin to monitor, control and optimize its functions, continuously predicting its future states. A DT is continuously interacting with its physical twin and its environment, exchanging data in real time. This definition does consider the three

elements proposed by Grieves: i) physical entity, ii) virtual entity and iii) relationship between both.

During the last years DTs have widely attracted the attention from both academia and industry. They are being used in a wide variety of domains such as manufacturing [31], agriculture [20], healthcare [23], etc. This explains why it is considered a strategic trend whose market is expected to grow at a 38% annually to reach \$16 billion by 2023 [9].

According to [32] this massive growth is caused by advances in the key enabling technologies that can be exploited for DT such as Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence, Big Data, Cloud Computing, real-time sensors, virtualizations, multi-agents, etc. It is worth highlighting that one of such technologies, multi-agent systems, resemble DT in many features. Multi-Agent Systems (MAS) are agent-based systems that act as an external entity operating in a specific environment while exploring and collecting data [7][25]. These agents are widely used to simulate complex environments where they coordinate and cooperate or compete to achieve common goals [22][30]. Normally, the agents have the following properties [39]:

- Autonomy: agents operate without the direct intervention of humans.
- Reactivity: agents perceive their environment and respond in a timely manner to the changes that occur in it.
- Proactivity: agents are able to make decisions to achieve their goals.
- Social competence: agents interact with other agents, and perhaps with humans as well and their interaction patterns evolve throughout the time.

The exploitation of MAS is thus a good approach to develop software entities that can represent and mimic the behavior of real-world entities. These features offered by MAS make them proper candidates for the development of DT. Some authors have already sketched this idea. For instance, Minerva et al. [25] comment on the direct correlation that exists between an agent and a logical object (the digital part of the DT) as both represent physical entities. These authors also highlight that MAS can be used to simulate the behaviour of a specific environment, which is one of the most relevant functions of the DT. On the other hand, as Grieves described [11], a digital twin consists of multiple entities and virtual environments, where each one has an objective to fulfil. Jones et al. [14] highlights the potential of MAS to integrate and control the DTs. As can be seen, there are several similarities between agents and digital twins, so many of the issues addressed in the development of MAS should be considered as valuable contributions to the development of DT.

In the literature, there are some relevant papers that explore the digital twin field. Some papers [2, 8, 14, 25] have elaborated literature reviews with the aim of reviewing the definitions of Digital Twin published so far in the literature, as well as the main characteristics that a DT must have or which areas DT applications have been developed for. However, our paper differs from those works in different ways. Firstly, regarding the methodology of the study, a systematic review has been carried out without establishing any specific time frame. Then, the papers analyzed do not belong to any specific field of application, so that different domains have been considered in this work. And finally, it is important to highlight that this study focuses on digital twins

as a concept linked to multi-agent systems. We are fully aware of the influence that other technologies may have on DT, but they are out of the scope of this work.

3. Methodology

In order to conduct this study, the guidelines proposed by Kitchenham et al. [18] have been applied. Therefore, we first defined the research question to be answered with this work:

RQ: How do current proposals exploit multi-agent systems to support those features expected in a digital twin?

Then, as shown in Fig. 2, we defined as search string “Digital twin”, as well as two alternative wordings to find any work related to MAS. We used Scopus as search engine, as it is the one that provides more detailed information about the papers. The query was conducted in November 2021 and resulted in a corpus of literature related to digital twin and multi-agents.

Fig. 2. Search Methodology.

The corpus, made up by 74 papers, was stored for their review using the inclusion/exclusion criteria listed below what come up with a corpus of 27 papers. A

paper is selected if it meets all the inclusion criteria, while a paper is discarded if it fails to meet any of the exclusion criteria. The inclusion criteria defined in this paper are as follows:

- CI1: Papers that include multi-agent systems proposals to address the development of Digital Twins.
- CI2: Papers in English.
- CI3: Peer reviewed papers in conferences and journals.
- CI4: Papers that provide information relevant to our scope.

On the other hand, the exclusion criteria defined in this paper are as follows. Table 1 shows how many papers have been excluded for each exclusion criterion.

- CE1: Papers in a language other than English.
- CE2: The study is a non-peer reviewed publication such as a technical report, editorial note, preface, index, introduction, presents a special / theme issue, or it is unreferenced, illegible, or inaccessible (e.g., paper is not available through the search engines used).
- CE3: Books, unpublished papers, editorial notes, master's / degree works and doctoral theses (gray literature - Blogs, web pages).
- CE4: Papers that do not provide information relevant to our scope.

Table 1. Papers excluded for each exclusion criterion.

Exclusion criteria	Number of papers
CE1	5
CE2	15
CE3	15
CE4	12

The final corpus contains 27 papers. Fig. 3 shows a breakdown of the corpus of papers selected according to the year in which they were published. The large rise in the number of publications in 2020 is evident. Regarding the smaller number of papers in 2021, we believe that this is because the papers are not yet indexed by the scientific engine used for the search since their date of publication is recent. In the following Section the analysis of the selected papers is presented.

Fig. 3. Number of papers by year.

Fig. 4 shows a breakdown of the corpus of papers which have been selected according to the type of publication of the papers. Most of the selected papers have been published in conferences.

Fig. 4. Number of papers by type of publication.

Once presented the corpus of papers selected by following a systematic process, in the next section a thorough analysis is included.

4. Discussion

To answer the RQ defined, this Section presents the outcomes of the analysis of the papers related to the use of multi-agent systems for the design of digital twins. This analysis has been conducted using the set of essential properties that digital twins must have according to Minerva et al. [25]. These properties can be classified into two groups: i) fundamental characteristics of digital twins and ii) characteristics that add value to DT. The first set of fundamental characteristics ensures that the digital twins adequately represent the physical asset and behaves in the same way as the physical assets in a given context. This set consists of three properties:

- *Representativeness and contextualization*: The digital twin should be as close as possible to its physical twin; however, it is difficult to fully represent it and sometimes it may be even unnecessary. Therefore, the digital twin should have only those attributes that are actually relevant for its context of use. This is especially pertinent when the DT is used in a particular environment, being more likely that only a subset of all the attributes is important.
- *Reflection*: this property indicates that all relevant attributes of the physical entity must be represented in a timely manner in the digital twin. The digital twin updates its state after collecting data from the physical world, being its state complete when all the data has been updated. Thus, the state of the digital twin is the same as that of the physical entity.
- *Entanglement*: it is a fundamental property of digital twins since it refers to the communication relationship between the digital and the physical twin. The exchange of information among them must be instantaneous (in real time).

The properties that provide added value to the DT are the following:

- *Replication*: digital twin can be replicated several times in different environments. This property refers to the ability to clone a physical entity in the digital world depending on the context.
- *Persistency*: the digital twin must be persistent and resistant over time, so that it is always available.
- *Memorization*: this property refers to the ability of the digital twin to store all past and present data of the physical twin. This data reflects the dynamics of the object itself and the context in which it operates.
- *Composability*: this property refers to the ability to group several objects into a composite, so that the behavior of the composite object, as well as that of the individual components, can be observed and controlled. If the digital twin represents a complex entity, there must be an efficient way to integrate new components into it.
- *Accountability/Manageability*: this property refers to the ability to manage digital twins accurately and completely. For example, in case of failure in the physical part, the digital twin must provide solutions to that failure by helping its recovery.

- *Augmentation*: the digital twin initially contains the relevant attributes of its physical twin for the context in which it works, but if the context changes, new attributes and functionality could be added as needed.
- *Ownership*: there are two types of ownership, on the one hand, the one that refers to the owner of the digital twin data, and on the other hand, the one that refers to the owner of the digital twin and the physical twin, which may not be the same.
- *Servitization*: the digital twin provides services to the physical world to be able to control the physical twin and operate in the real environment using actuators, for example.
- *Predictability*: this property refers to the ability of the digital twin to simulate the behavior of its physical twin in a specific environment and interact with other objects in that environment.

In the following, we analyze whether the digital twin proposed in the papers identified in Section 3 support the properties described above. Table 2 and Table 3 show a summary of this analysis, identifying which properties are supported by each paper. It has not been possible to determine which properties of digital twins are supported by papers [3][13][24][28][40]. This is because these papers focus their research on the design of an architecture that enables the integration of these technologies in industry, but they do not describe their own digital twins. On the other hand, Minerva et al. [25] discuss all the properties that a DT should have and suggest the use of multi-agent systems for its development, but does not describe how to use them for constructing digital twins.

From Table 2 and Table 3 the first conclusion that can be drawn is that not all the properties defined in [25] are supported by the digital twins proposed in the papers analyzed. However, the three features that form the set of fundamental properties (*representativeness and contextualization, reflection, and entanglement*) are supported by most of the proposals. This indicates that when defining and modeling a digital twin using multi-agent systems it is also essential to have good connectivity between the physical world and cyberspace so that the data exchange between the digital twin (or agent) and the physical part is instantaneous. And it should also be noted that the digital twin should be as similar as possible to the physical twin, with all the relevant attributes of the physical twin being represented in a timely manner in the digital twin for each context.

On the other hand, we argue below why we believe that some of the properties of the second subset, defined in [25] as value added, are more accepted than others. As can be seen in Table 2 and Table 3, the two properties of this subset that are addressed by more papers are *memorization* and *predictability*. Regarding the *memorization* property, it is logical that many proposals consider it because massive volumes of data are generated with these technologies, and these data are used by agents to make better decisions based on them in real time. Moreover, the *predictability* property refers to the interaction among DTs as well as between DT and other objects. Given that DTs are being studied jointly with MAS, it was expected that this property was included in most of the proposals, since multi-agent systems are characterized by the easy interaction both among agents as well as between agents and other objects of the environment.

Table 2. Analysis of properties of Digital Twins extracted from [25] supported by the selected papers (I/II).

Properties	[1]	[5]	[6]	[10]	[12]	[15]	[16]	[17]	[19]	[20]	[21]
Representativeness and contextualization	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Reflection	✓		✓	✓	✓		✓			✓	
Entanglement	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Replication			✓		✓		✓	✓			
Persistency					✓						
Memorization	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓		✓	✓
Composability											
Accountability/ Manageability											
Augmentation					✓			✓			
Ownership								✓			
Servitization	✓		✓	✓	✓						
Predictability	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Table 3. Analysis of properties of Digital Twins extracted from [25] supported by the selected papers (II/II).

Properties	[26]	[27]	[29]	[31]	[33]	[34]	[35]	[36]	[37]	[38]
Representativeness and contextualization	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Reflection					✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Entanglement		✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓
Replication					✓	✓	✓			
Persistency										
Memorization	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Composability										
Accountability/ Manageability										
Augmentation			✓							
Ownership										
Servitization										
Predictability		✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Other properties, such as *replication*, *augmentation* and *servitization*, are considered in few proposals. The first one, *replication*, is included in those papers where the authors needed to have more than one digital twin for the same physical asset, because they have to be used in different contexts. For example, in [35] authors develop DTs of plants for precision agriculture management. Since authors consider that the context of

the plant changes according to its development stage, they create a different DT for the same plant for each one of such stages. The *augmentation* property is included in those papers, where they propose that, in the future, their digital twins will be enriched to consider other characteristics or to be able to perform other functions that may be needed in new contexts. For example, manufacturing industries are moving towards mass customization, where each customized product is represented by a DT [29]. In these cases, new features or functions may be added in the future to the DT to further personalize the product. Finally, in some papers, their digital twins can act on the physical world, so they comply with the *servitization* property. For example, also in the field of manufacturing, in [10] they describe how real objects are turned into intelligent objects that incorporate self-management capabilities. This facilitates that if the DT detects an anomaly in its behavior, it can address it, for example, by stopping the production and, thus, avoiding further losses.

The *persistency* and *ownership* properties are each one considered in just one paper. As aforementioned, *persistency* states that the DT must be always available throughout time. In [12] authors discuss a case study of DTs in the healthcare domain. DTs act when an anomaly is detected in the patient's medical parameters alerting the user so that he can take the appropriate measures. Therefore, in this paper they emphasize the importance of the DT being always available over time. Regarding *ownership*, there are two types of owners, on the one hand, the owner of the DT data, and on the other hand, the owner of the DT. In [17] they refer to the second type by analyzing how personal DTs can replace a person in some activities. The authors provide some facilities that can be used by a person to create his own DT, so that the owner of such DT is his creator. Finally, the properties *composability* and *accountability/manageability* are not supported by any of the proposals analyzed.

Table 4. Properties of agents extracted from [39] satisfied by the whole set of 27 papers analyzed.

Properties of agents	Summary
Autonomy	Humans do not participate in the agent's decisions.
Reactivity	Agents perceive the environment with the data provided by the DT.
Proactivity	Agents make decisions based on the DT's data.
Social competence	Agents interact with each other.

Additionally, the same set of 27 papers are also analyzed from the point of view of the characteristics expected for multi-agent systems as discussed in [39]. This analysis is summarized in Table 4. As can be observed, people do not participate in the decisions made by the agents defined in the analyzed papers, in other words, the agents they use have *autonomy*, and the physical-cybernetic convergence is complete. This is also achieved thanks to the use of DT. In the proposals studied, the data captured from the physical world by the sensors deployed are essential for the agents to be *reactive* and *proactive*. All these data are collected by the DT, justifying why the *memorization* property of DT was included in most of the proposals, as we pointed out above. Finally, it is worth highlighting the existing relationship between the property of *predictability*

of DT and the property of *social competence* of the agents, since both refer to the interaction between themselves, and even with people so it was expected that all the papers analyzed satisfy such property.

After analyzing the DT and MAS proposals by using the properties identified in [25] and [39], we also analyzed how both technologies interplay in these papers. But first of all, we would like to emphasize that integrating multiagent systems with digital twins can be a challenging task because the distinction is sometimes blurred. Considering this issue several conclusions can be drawn:

- Some papers ([3][10][20][24][31][33][34][35][37]) use ontologies (key semantic component of the MAS) to organize the knowledge of the physical asset in the cyberworld, which is fed by real data obtained by the DT. In these cases, ontologies are used as a tool to digitize the knowledge of the environment and of the physical twins needed by the agents to make decisions. Also, this way of managing knowledge using ontologies is used to improve and facilitate the interaction between different agents.
- In other papers ([6][19][27][16]), DTs are seen just as a database. In these cases, DTs of the various physical entities constitute large knowledge databases that the agents can observe, making decisions based on such information as well as also acting on the DT.
- Other papers ([4][5][17]) comment that when a DT has an objective to fulfill, then such DT is developed as an agent, being modeled the environment in which all the DT operate as a multi-agent system.
- Finally, other papers ([1][15][26]) need to define different types of DTs that must interact in a specific environment. Then, such environment is provided by a multi-agent system where DTs can interact with each other.

In general, digital twins and multi-agent systems are in essence integrated in two ways: i) DTs get real-time data from physical entities and these data is used by agents to make better decisions, and ii) multi-agent systems are the interaction environment of DTs.

5. Conclusion and future work

In this paper we report the results of a literature review about digital twins and their interplay with multi-agent systems in order to understand and deepen the synergies between them. The systematic process followed led us to identify a collection of 74 papers related to DTs and MAS in Scopus database. Once these papers were filtered by applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria specified, a final corpus of 27 papers was selected. It is undeniable that DTs and MAS are two terms that have attracted the interest of the research community in recent years. The number of publications related to both terms in 2020 far exceeds the number of publications in previous years.

In the analysis of the corpus, we first discussed whether the current proposals for DTs feature the properties a DT should have according to [25] and then the same has been done for the characteristics of MAS indicated in [39]. After this initial analysis

was done, synergies between both were studied, two of which stand out: on the one hand, the DT *memorization* property, which refers to the ability of the DT to store all the data of the physical twin, is used by the agents of the MAS to exploit these data to make better decisions. This helps the agents in becoming both reactive and proactive. On the other hand, the *predictability* property of the DTs, related to the interaction between DTs and humans, is equivalent to the *social competence* of agents. This enables MAS to provide an interaction environment for the DTs. To sum up, in the current proposals of DTs where MAS are used, the MAS are the environment where the different DTs interact, and additionally the data of the DTs allow agents to make better decisions in real time.

Regarding our future work, it would be interesting to identify which extensions to current MAS proposals would be necessary to provide a comprehensive proposal for DT. The proposals identified in this paper that offer most of the properties desirable in the implementation of DTs are our starting point. On the other hand, given that there is an upward trend in the number of publications related to DT and MAS, the work could be updated in the coming years to see how the proposals evolve. Also, we are considering exploiting other search engines using the same query and replicate the work done to try to identify a larger number of papers.

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